

Acknowledgement

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References

1. F. G. MANN and B. C. SAUNDERS, "Practical Organic Chemistry", The English Language Book Society, IV Ed., 1974, p. 349.
2. N. N. SINGH and K. S. BOPARAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 1143.
3. N. N. SINGH and K. S. BOPARAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 1193.
4. J. BERGER, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, 8, 429.
5. J. R. CLARK and S. M. WANG, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 1230.
6. J. BERGER, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1952, 6, 1564.
7. J. KUCHARSKY and L. SAFARIK, "Titrations in non-aqueous Solvents", Elsevier Publishing Company, Amsterdam, 1965, p. 99.

Further Studies on the Structure and Stereochemistry of Entagenic acid

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EARLIER the structure of entagenic acid, a new sapogenin isolated from the seeds of *entada phaseoloides* Merrill (Syn. *E. scandens*, *E. pурсае-tha*), was proposed as 3 β , 21 α , 22 α -trihydroxy olean-12-ene-28-oic acid¹⁻³. Later in a short communication⁴ a revised structure, 3 β , 15 α , 16 α -trihydroxy olean-12-ene-28-oic acid (Ia), was proposed. Recently Wen Chin Lin *et al.*⁵ have isolated a glycoside of entagenic acid from *E. phaseoloides* which has been shown to have significant antitumour activity against 256 carcinoma in rats. The present paper describes further work which confirms structure (Ia) for entagenic acid.

It has been shown earlier⁴ that methyl entagenate on acetylation at 0° yields mainly diacetyl methyl entagenate and 3-acetyl methyl entagenate. A very small amount of triacetyl methyl entagenate is also formed. The diacetyl methyl entagenate was considered earlier to be a 3, 15-diacetate (Ib).

It was thought that if the diacetate was a 3,15-diacetate (Ib) then on dehydration by treatment with POCl₃ in pyridine on steam bath, it would lead to the formation of a 15-keto compound (II) as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

With this objective the above reaction was carried out. On working up a major product, C₂₃H₅₀O₅ (M⁺ 526), m.p. 192°, and another product in traces, C₂₃H₅₀O₅ (M⁺ 526), m.p. 203°, were obtained. The mass spectral fragmentation pattern (see Scheme 2) of the former (m.p. 192°) is typical of a 15-keto compound⁶ and hence the structure of the compound must be (II). If the keto group was not at 15 then instead of a peak at m/e 277 a peak at m/e 276 would have been observed due to normal r-D.A. fragmentation.

Scheme-2

The formation of the 15-keto compound (II) clearly locates the α -glycol system in entagenic acid at 15,

16-positions. This also supports the earlier stereochemical assignment of the α -glycol system in entagenic acid.

The second product (m.p. 203°) was characterised as 3-acetyl-16-keto methyl olean-12-ene-28-oate (III) by direct comparison of m.p., mixed m.p., TLC and IR spectrum with an authentic sample prepared by oxidation of 3-acetyl methyl echinocystate available in our laboratory. The formation of 16-keto compound (III), though in traces, is rather interesting. There may be two alternative explanations; (i) that the diacetate described earlier may contain mainly the 3,15-diacetate and trace of 3,16-diacetate formed by acyl migration during column chromatography, for such acyl migrations are known to occur^{7,8}, (ii) The acyl migration takes place during the process of dehydration. The second process appears to be more probable since the diacetate showed single spot in TLC over silica gel G and also over AgNO₃-impregnated silica gel G plates in various solvent systems. Incidentally it may be pointed out that Djerassi *et al.*⁹ has reported that the 15 α (equatorial) -OH group undergoes easy dehydration to give 15, 16-double bond whereas the dehydration of 15 β (axial) OH group leads to rearranged product (cf. Dumortierigenin).

The conversion of methyl entagenate to 3-acetyl 15-keto methyl olean-12-ene-28-oate (II) together with the earlier data⁴ conclusively proves the structure and stereochemistry of entagenic acid as 3 β , 15 α , 16 α -trihydroxy olean-12-ene-28-oic acid (Ia).

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References

1. A. K. BARUA, *Naturwiss.*, 1956, 43, 250.
2. A. K. BARUA, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, 23, 1499.
3. A. K. BARUA, P. CHAKRABARTI and B. C. DAS, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, 23, 1505.
4. A. K. BARUA, P. CHAKRABARTI, S. K. PAL and B. C. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 195.
5. W. C. LIN, M. KUGELMANN, R. A. WILSON and K. V. RAO, *Phytochem.*, 1972, 11, 171.
6. H. BUDZIKIEWICZ, J. M. WILSON and C. DJERASSI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 3688.
7. I. YOSIOKA, T. NISHIMA, N. WATANI and I. KITAGAWA, *T. Letters*, 1968, 55.
8. O. D. HEUSENS and K. G. LEWIS, *T. Letters*, 1968, 3213.
9. C. DJERASSI, C. H. ROBINSON and D. B. THOMAS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 5685.

Chemical Investigations of the leaves of *Calicarpa arborea* (Verbenaceae)

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IN a previous communication¹ we reported the isolation of betulinic acid, baurenol and β -sitosterol from the bark of *Calicarpa arborea*. The isolation of ursolic acid, epilupeol and β -sitosterol from the leaves of the same plant is reported in this paper.

Air dried and powdered leaves of *C. arborea* were exhaustively extracted with hot benzene for 18 hrs. The benzene extract was separated into neutral and acidic fractions. The acidic fraction on repeated chromatography over a column of silica gel afforded from benzene-ethylacetate (4:1) eluate an amorphous solid, m. p. 240-245°. It gave positive Leibermann-Burchardt test. It was then esterified with diazomethane and then acetylated (Ac₂O/Py) and then chromatographed over de-activated alumina and finally crystallised from a mixture of CHCl₃-MeOH. The acetate, m. p. 244-47° was identified as acetyl methyl ursolate by comparison (mixed m.p., TLC and I.R.) with an authentic specimen.

The neutral fraction was chromatographed over a column of silica gel. After a forerun of waxy material, elution with a mixture of petrol-C₆H₆ (7:3) furnished a solid, m.p. 138-42°. This on chromatography over silica gel impregnated with AgNO₃ yielded an amorphous solid, m.p. 145-50°, which could not be crystallised; ν_{max} 3250, 880 cm⁻¹; MS m/e 426 (M⁺), 408 (M-H₂O)⁺, 393 (M-H₂O-CH₃)⁺, 207, 218 (base peak) and 189. It was acetylated and the crude acetate on chromatography followed by crystallisation from CHCl₃-MeOH yielded a crystalline solid, C₃₁H₅₂O₉, m.p. 157-60° (lit.³ m.p. 163°); ν_{max} 1725, 1220 and 880 cm⁻¹; MS m/e 468 (M⁺), 408 (M-AcOH)⁺, 393 (M-CH₃-HOAc)⁺, 249, 218 (base peak) and 189 suggesting its identity with epilupeol⁴. Finally its identity with epi-lupeol was confirmed by comparison (TLC and I.R.) with an authentic specimen⁵.

Further elution of the column with petrol-C₆H₆ (2:3) afforded a solid which on acetylation and crystallisation furnished β -sitosteryl acetate, C₃₁H₅₂O₉, m.p. 126-128° (lit.⁶ m.p. 127-28°), identical (mixed m.p., TLC and I.R.) with an authentic specimen.

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